
APPLICATION OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract Discussion of teaching science, teaching methodology, foreign language teaching methodology, foreign language teaching methodology, foreign language teaching methodology, types of modern methods and future problems.

Key words: methodology, innovation, foreign language, communication, skills, competence, didactics.

After our country gained independence, democratic life began to be established in Uzbekistan from the first years of independence. The economy was also important. The weight of the implemented reforms is increasing year by year. Not only radical reforms, but also many changes in other areas, including the education system. In particular, interest in teaching foreign languages has increased and many conditions have been created for young people. The main goal is to increase the level of knowledge of young people and increase their interest in foreign languages. As the first President Islam Karimov noted: "Teaching foreign languages is gaining great importance in our country today. We should not overestimate the importance of perfect knowledge of foreign languages for our nation, which is building its great future in solidarity and cooperation with our foreign partners. on events" was adopted. This decision further expanded the possibilities of learning foreign languages. Today, the demand for foreign languages is increasing. [Methodological Journal of the Ministry of Public Education, 2019.53.] **DISCUSSION AND RESULTS** Currently, it is necessary to search for and test new methods of teaching not only in foreign language teaching, but also in all subjects. is being implemented. This is one of the most important problems that must be solved in order to improve the educational process today.

If previously teaching a foreign language was considered to be the study of this language system, in the following years the main goal of teaching became the development of students' speech in a foreign language. It should be said that these goals in learning a foreign language are not set by themselves or other people or individuals, but are closely related to changes in linguistics and psychology and social development of society. For example: Let's take the audiolingual method. The emergence of this style was influenced by changes in linguistics, i.e. structural flow. It includes the following factors: - teaching a foreign language should begin with teaching oral speech;

- language teaching is carried out on the basis of various structures and forms of speech;
- exercises also require language exercises that require repeated repetition of language material; - Grammatical models and the choice of vocabulary should depend on the results of comparing the foreign language with the native language - Pronunciation requires a lot of attention. The main disadvantage of this method is the large number of mechanical exercises and the lack of real speech exercises. The founders of this method are methodologists C. Friz and R. Ladolar. For example: C. Freeze says that the main content of the initial stage should be the study of structures. It is desirable that it be based on the formation of grammar skills [Sh. Alimov 2017.2 p.] Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted education, in the process of which a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, there is a process of comparing the native language with a foreign language. Various teaching methods and technologies are used in this process.

Using modern pedagogical technologies, learning a foreign language in comparison with the native language gives effective results. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methods and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. There are different methods of teaching methodology. The methods of teaching a foreign language are widely used: the communicative-didactic method, the method of organizing intercultural communication and the method of organizing exercises. Due to the high level of cooperation between foreign partners and specialists in various fields, their need for language learning is high. Currently, foreign languages are taught in schools, colleges, lyceums and universities. There are innovative learning materials for those who want to learn languages at different levels. Mastering a foreign language and gaining a certain level also depends on the practical methods and qualifications of the teachers.

Information technology and modern teaching methods, the ability to apply help to quickly understand new material. By combining different methods, the teacher has the opportunity to make decisions about specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the ability to choose the most effective ways to achieve goals is formed. In this regard, the use of many teaching and learning methods is effective. Nowadays, innovation is increasing in all fields. [Feruza Zaipova, Sabohat Orinova Khorizhiy, p. 2] In teaching a foreign language, based on the student's potential and level, step-by-step teaching is effective. 2 is divided into groups based on intermediate level preparation. , 3 at a higher level. For each stage, the teacher develops a special active program. Active educational methods not only help to encourage students to think and practice actively in the learning process, but also form positive pedagogical motivation, reveal and develop creative abilities. helps, learns the material with high efficiency, helps mastering. At each stage of the lesson, active methods

should be used that are effective not only for the teacher, but also for the students. I recommend that you familiarize yourself with some of them.

Almost all techniques are dynamic and can be used not only in foreign language classes, but also in other subjects. 1. Organizational stage. "Carousel" ("Carousel") This method allows you to use imaginative thinking and memory. The first student takes a card from the teacher and names associations with this word. The card is passed down the chain until it is returned to the teacher. Each student has the opportunity to express his opinion quickly. At this stage, students "memorize" the material. The principle of "Intellectual warm-up" can be used in the classroom to develop speaking skills. As a rule, the lexical basis of such exercises is located on the board, especially at the initial stage. A snowball can grow in two directions: with an increase in vocabulary and/or an increase in the complexity of grammar. (EXAMPLE: I like to read books. I like to read e-books. I like to read e-books because they are easy to use). Working with flashcards Review past material in flashcard view. This method helps to organize the material and regain the attention of students. CONCLUSION As a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, students develop logical thinking skills, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to answer quickly and correctly is formed. Such methods and games create a desire for knowledge in the student. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students the subject of the learning process. The effectiveness of using different tables in the process of teaching a foreign language is also high. Using tables in the learning process, students can learn a certain grammar rule, for example, making sentences using tenses, arranging new words. At a time when the need to learn a foreign language is high, the effective use of modern information technologies and innovative educational technologies in the educational process has effectively implemented this process. The effectiveness of innovative educational technologies lies in their correct and effective use in the educational process [Otoboeva M.R. 2017.36-37].

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